

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

SURFACE LAYER OF YBCO CRYSTALS

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Abstract

The article presents a model of the thickness of the surface layer of YBCO crystals, from which its domain structure follows. It is shown that in the surface nanolayer, the temperature of the transition to the superconducting state increases by 2 times compared to the bulk phase. Lamels in the monodomain are determined as Abrikosov vortices, and there are 15 of them in the surface layer of YBCO.

Keywords: Superconductivity, surface layer, nanostructure, crystal.

Introduction

At the beginning of the 21st century, in his work [1], V.L. Ginzburg outlined the history of superconductivity research in three periods: “the day before yesterday (1911-1941), yesterday (1942-1986),

and today (1987-?)”. The present period is actively developing at the present time, this is especially related to high-temperature superconductivity (SC) of cuprates (Table 1).

Table 1.

Experimental values of the SC transition temperature in cuprates.

Chemical compound	T _c , K	Chemical compound	T _c , K	Chemical compound	T _c , K
La _{1.8} Sr _{0.2} CuO ₄	36 [2]	Tl ₂ Ba ₂ CuO ₆ Tl ₂ Ba ₂ Cu ₂ (CaO ₈) Tl ₂ Ba ₂ Cu ₃ (Ca ₂ O ₁₀) Tl ₂ Ba ₂ Ca ₃ Cu ₄ O ₁₂	80 [5]	HgBa ₂ CuO _{4.12}	97 [7]
YBa ₂ Cu ₃ O _{7-δ}	93 [3]		108 [6]	HgBa ₂ CaCu ₂ O ₆	127 [7]
Bi ₂ Sr ₂ Cu ₂ (CaO ₈)	86 [4]		120 [6]	HgBa ₂ Cu ₃ (Ca ₂ O ₈)	138 [7]
Bi ₂ Sr ₂ Cu ₃ (Ca ₂ O ₁₆)	108 [4] 120 [5]		102 [5]		[7]

The highest superconductor is achieved in mercury cuprates – 138 K (Table 1). More recently [8], Korean physicists Lee, Kim et al. reported the discovery of a superconductor at room temperature under ambient pressure: Pb_{10-x}Cu_x(PO₄)₆O with 0.9 < x < 1.1. They had previously named this material LK-99 after their initials and the year of the first synthesis. In the same year (2023), a number of articles [9-11] appeared that cast doubt on the results of [8]. We will not delve into the listed works, but will consider the

classic example of YBa₂Cu₃O_{7-δ}, otherwise known as YBCO material.

The aim of this article is to model the surface layer of YBCO material and its properties.

Crystal structure of YBCO

Figure 1 a, b and c show the structures of the unit cells of YBCO in three main modifications corresponding to oxygen stoichiometries with indices 6, 6.5 and 7 [12].

Figure 1. YBCO structure: a) – tetragonal, b) – orthorhombic II, c) – orthorhombic I [12].

Table 2 shows the unit cell parameters of YBCO structures.

Table 2.

Optimized lattice parameters (a, b and c) [13]			
	a, Å	b, Å	c, Å
$\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$	3.820	3.885	11.681
$\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.75}$	3.836	3.911	11.969
$\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$	3.845	3.886	12.000
$\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.25}$	3.846	3.898	12.087
$\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_6$	3.865	3.865	12.159

It follows from Table 2 that the parameters a, b and c change insignificantly, but oxygen non-stoichiometry leads to a deviation from the BCS theory, and the main contribution comes from the interaction through longitudinal optical vibrations of oxygen in the CuO_2 plane [13, 14]. The conductivity of the CuO_2 oxide layers arises as a result of the quasi-two-dimensional

delocalization of the charge states in these (see Fig. 2) planes [12].

It is proposed [15] to consider intermediate structures of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_y$ at $y = 0.1$ as microdomains, consisting of alternating sections with tetragonal and rhombic ordering (see Fig. 1).

Figure 2. Projection of the crystal structure of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ onto the (100) plane and a schematic representation of the overlap of the electron orbitals of copper and oxygen ions (a); dependence of T_c on the oxygen content (b) [12].

"High-temperature superconductivity in cuprates is born directly from the "strange" metallic state [16-20], which is characterized by a linearized temperature resistance up to the highest measured temperatures."

YBCO Surface Layer Thickness

The surface layer thickness $R(I)$ is given by us by the formula [21]:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot \nu \text{ [m]}. \quad (1)$$

In equation (1) one parameter must be known – the molar volume of the element, which is equal to $v = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is its density), $\alpha = 1 \text{ m}^{-2}$ is a

constant to maintain the dimensionality ($R(I) \text{ [m]}$). The diagram of a solid is shown in Fig. 3a and in Fig. 3b – the dependence of v in the periodic table.

Figure 3. Scheme of a solid: nanolayer → mesolayer → bulk phase (a); dependence of molar volume in the periodic table.

Equation (1) turned out to be valid for determining the layer thickness of: d-elements [22]; alkali metal halides [23]; ferroelectric crystals [24]; porous silicon [25]; high-entropy alloy [26]; lanthanide and actinide crystals [27]; natural minerals [28].

In [29] it was shown that the surface energy of a bulk metal γ_2 with an accuracy of 3% is equal to:

$$\gamma_2 = 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \text{ [J/m}^2\text{]}, \quad (2)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the metal (K).

In the $R(I)$ layer, the size effect must be taken into account and the surface energy of the $R(I)$ layer becomes equal to γ_1 [30]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 (1 - R(I)/R(I) + h) \approx 0,3\gamma_2, \quad (3)$$

where γ_{12} is the surface energy at the phase boundary, which is negligibly small due to the second-order phase transition.

To separate the $R(I)$ layer from the rest of the crystal, energy must be expended, which is called the adhesion energy [30]:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2. \quad (4)$$

Internal stresses σ_{is} between phases γ_1 and γ_2 can be calculated using the formula [31]:

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot \bar{L} / R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is Young's modulus of elasticity.

Another formula [32] that will be useful to us further:

$$\begin{aligned} A(r)/A(\infty) &= 1 - R(I)/r, \quad r \gg R(I), \\ A(r)/A(\infty) &= 1 - R(I)/R(I) + r, \quad 0 \leq r \leq R(I), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $A(r)$ is the physical property of the nano- and mesolayer with coordinate r ; $A(\infty)$ is the physical property of the bulk sample (bulk phase) (Fig. 3a).

Using equations (1)-(5), we calculate the parameters for YBCO.

Table 3.

Parameters $R(I)$ for YBCO

Element	M , g/mol	ρ , g/sm ³	$R(I)_{a=b}$, nm	$R(I)_c$, nm	γ_a , mJ/m ²	γ_c , mJ/m ²
YBCO	666,19	6,3	6 (15)	18 (15)	905	302
Y	88,91	4,47	3,38 (9)	5,31 (9)	1257	801
Ba	137,327	3,78	6,18 (12)	-	1337	-
Cu	63,546	8,92	1,21 (3)	-	950	-

The surface energy γ was determined by formula (2), knowing $T_m = 1293 \text{ K}$ for YBCO from [33]. The number in brackets gives the number of monolayers in the compound $n = R(I)/a$ (a is the lattice constant). Table 3 shows that YBCO, Y, Ba, Cu crystals have a layer thickness $R(I)$ from 1.21 nm (Cu) to 18 nm (YBCO), i.e. they fall into the nanoregion according to Gleiter [34]. The layer $R(II) \approx 9 R(I)$, which we called

the mesolayer, extends to the bulk phase (Fig. 3a). The layers $R(I)$ and $R(II)$ differ in the nature of the size effects [21]. There are no size effects in the bulk phase. The difference between mesostructures and nanostructures and the bulk phase is that only in these systems are flicker noises with a spectrum of the $1/f^b$ type observed [35, 36]. Using formulas (1) – (5), we calculate the elastic parameters of YBCO (Table 4).

Table 4.

Elastic parameters of YBCO						
	W_{aa} , J/m ²	W_{ac} , J/m ²	σ_{isa} , MPa	σ_{isc} , MPa	E_a , GPa	E_c , GPa
YBCO	1,18	0,39	5069	985	130,6 [37]	43,7
Graphite	2,853	1,690	4900	1360	7,59	3,48

Table 4 shows, as an example, the elastic parameters of graphite [38], which also has a layered structure.

Large internal stresses σ in the R(I) layer lead to relaxation or reconstruction of the crystal surface (including YBCO) (Fig. 4) [39].

Domain structure of YBCO

Figure 4. Transformation of the metal surface: relaxation – upper layer (a, b); reconstruction – several layers (c, d)

On the relaxed surface, a change in the interplanar distances c is observed, while on the reconstructed surface, the arrangement of the near-surface atoms can change (Fig. 4). Relaxation processes are characteristic of the surfaces of fcc metals (such as Al, Au, Ni), while reconstruction processes are characteristic of bcc metals (Fe, W, Mo). In the R(I) layer, due to high internal stresses, the following arise: Frenkel and Schottky defects [40], the merging of which forms pores; dislocations, the merging of which forms cracks [40]. Nano-cracks were experimentally discovered in [41, 42]. Their method is based on fractoluminescence, when a light signal (luminescence) occurs during the destruction of a solid when atomic bonds on the surface of nano-cracks are broken with a time resolution of 1 to 2 nanoseconds. In [30, 43], we proposed a new analytical model for calculating the length of nanocracks that occur in crystals. For the first time, the parameters of nanocracks were calculated using atomically smooth metals as an example. The results obtained using the developed technique were compared with the results of using known models of microcrack formation. It was shown that our results are consistent with previously known results.

The result of the results obtained was that the length of a nanocrack $L_{nm} = R(I)$. It follows from this that the size of a nanodomain in the R(I) YBCO layer is equal to $D = L_{nm} = R(I)$. From Table 3, it follows that $D_{a-b} = 6$ nm, $D_c = 18$ nm, and the number of lamellas (the number of monolayers) in a monodomain is 15. In [44], the formation of nanodomains with two characteristic sizes (3–6 and 8–15 nm) was noted in structures with ultrafine InGaN insertions using the STM method. Similar results were obtained in [45]. It was also established there that pulsed laser heating of lithium tantalate leads to the formation of regions with

different types of domain structures in the irradiated zone: domain rays and chains, a labyrinth structure, and isolated domains. The geometric parameters of the structures and the sizes of the regions depend on the initial temperature of the crystal. In [43], we showed that the length of nanocracks obeys the condition: $L_{nm} \rightarrow L_{\mu m} = 10^2 L_{nm} \rightarrow L_C = 10^4 L_{nm}$, where the μm index corresponds to the mesolayer and C to the bulk (macro) phase. If we refer to Table 3, then for the layered YBCO crystal it follows that for the bulk phase $DC = 1.8$ μm . In [46], for YBCO, using the method of tunneling microscopy and spectroscopy, domain sizes from 1.12 to 2.1 μm were obtained with a change in the critical current density from 4.5 to 6.8 10^5 A/cm², which on average is 1.61 μm , which does not differ much from our value - 1.8 μm . The presented data confirm our model (1).

Superconductivity of the YBCO surface layer

Let us turn to the second formula (6) and set $A(r) = 1/T_c[R(I)]$ – the temperature of the transition to the superconducting state in the R(I) layer. From (6) we have:

$$T_c[R(I)] = 2 \cdot T_c(\infty) \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) shows that in the surface nanolayer the transition temperature to the superconducting state increases by a factor of 2 compared to the bulk phase. In [48], the heat capacity of lead embedded in nanometer pores of glass (7 nm in diameter) and bulk lead was studied in the temperature range of 2–40 K without a field and in magnetic fields up to 8 T; the properties of lead nanoparticles and bulk lead were compared. The results obtained made it possible to separate surface superconductivity from bulk superconductivity. It was shown that two superconducting transitions are observed in the

temperature dependence of the heat capacity of lead nanoparticles: above and below the transition temperature for bulk lead ($T_c = 7.2$ K), associated with surface and bulk superconductivity, and the upper

critical fields H_{c3} for surface and H_{c2} for bulk superconductivity were determined, which turned out to be greater for Pb nanoparticles than for bulk lead. In Fig. 5 shows the dependence of heat capacity [49].

Figure 5. Temperature dependences of the heat capacity of Pb embedded in nanometer pores of glass (1), Pb nanoparticles (2) and porous glass (3). The inset shows the heat capacity of Pb nanoparticles (4) and massive Pb (5) in the region of the superconducting transition [49].

The inset in Fig. 5 shows that in the superconducting transition region the heat capacity of Pb nanoparticles is greater than that of the bulk sample. If we designate the R(I) layers as phase I with surface energy γ_1 and the R(II) layer + bulk as phase II with surface energy γ_2 (formula (2)), then we have the following: isobaric heat capacity $C_P(I) = \Delta H/T_1 = \Delta H/\beta \gamma_1$, similarly $C_P(II) = \Delta H/\beta \gamma_2$, then $C_P(I)/C_P(II) = \gamma_2/\gamma_1 \approx 3$. This means that the heat capacity of a nanolayer or nanoparticle is 3 times greater than the heat capacity of the bulk metal, which confirms our model (1).

Separating surface superconductivity from bulk superconductivity is not so simple. In [49], the superconducting transition temperature in a FeSe crystal nanolayer grown on a SrTiO₃ substrate was $T_c = 20$ K instead of its bulk value $T_c = 7$ K.

In [50], direct evidence is presented of an increased superconducting T_c on the surface of cleaved Ba(Fe_{0.95}Co_{0.05})₂As₂ single crystals. Transport measurements performed on samples cleaved in ultrahigh vacuum show a significantly increased superconducting transition compared to equivalent measurements performed in air. Deviations from the bulk resistance appear at 21 K, which is significantly higher than the 10 K bulk T_c . These values are consistent with formula (7).

In [51], it is emphasized that surface superconductivity cannot be considered a negligibly small, "weak" effect. Surface superconductivity significantly screens the external magnetic field, and the density of registered, excited in the surface layer, undamped electric currents is commensurate with the density of "decoupling currents" of the volume superconductivity.

We will consider equation (7) to be valid and in the surface nanolayer the temperature of the transition to the superconducting state increases by 2 times compared to the bulk phase.

Abrikosov vortices in the surface layer of YBCO

In YBa₂Cu₃O_{6+x} crystals with oxygen content less than the nominal ($x < 1$), the critical temperature drops (Fig. 6; right curve), as does the concentration of free electrons. At $x < 0.4$, we are already dealing with a dielectric, in which, however, at sufficiently low temperatures, magnetic ordering of copper atoms is observed. The magnetic moments of neighboring copper atoms are oriented antiparallel, and the resulting magnetization of the crystal remains equal to zero [52]. This type of magnetic order is well known in the physics of magnetism and is called antiferromagnetic.

Figure 6. Phase diagram of $YBa_2Cu_3O_7$ [52]

Using the results obtained above, we define the lamellae in the monodomain as Abrikosov vortices [52], and there are 15 of them in the surface layer of YBCO. At low temperatures, these elementary vortices, due to the weak attraction between them, line up into domains, and then these lines form a vortex lattice. As the temperature increases, the vortex lines twist more and more due to thermal fluctuations, and at a certain temperature the vortex lattice melts.

Conclusion

The superconductivity of the YBCO surface layer still holds many mysteries: size effects, features of electron and hole motion, and much more. All these effects will be available for superconductors above room temperature.

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